

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MUSA****FIRST NAME: ABDULLAHI****PROGRAM CODE: DIFE****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 11%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D: INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING (DOCTORATE)

1. What is the key function of an academic essay?¹
 - To communicate evidence-based ideas by testing hypotheses.**
 - To serve as a platform for nonfictional creative storytelling.
 - To provide an overview of historical events.
 - To provide a researcher's personal opinions without the need for formal attribution.
2. Which of the following practices ensures that an author avoids plagiarism?²
 - Making sure that all sources of information are cited accurately.**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D. C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 7.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 34.

- Restricting all writings to personal opinions and experiences of previous authors.
 - Entirely avoiding direct quotes in academic writing.
 - Ensuring that contents borrowed from other authors are rephrased, even if they are not attributed.
3. Which of the following statements best describes the purpose of a style guide in academic writing?³
- To facilitate consistency and coherence in academic essays.**
 - To encourage the use of everyday language in academic essays.
 - To provide an opportunity for authors to combine multiple styles in one academic essay.
 - To entrench personal writing styles in academic essays.
4. Which of the following best describes a working hypothesis in dissertation research?⁴
- A working hypothesis guides the dissertation research using plausible answers.**
 - A working hypothesis must not change throughout the dissertation process.
 - A working hypothesis guides the conclusion of the dissertation.
 - A working hypothesis eliminates the need for data collection and analysis.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 41.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Ninth Edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), sec. 2.3.

5. Why is it important for a researcher to always acknowledge views that oppose theirs?⁵

Doing so demonstrates the researcher's knowledge and ability to perform a critical review, thus strengthening their arguments.

Doing so strengthens the researcher's hypothesis and secondary data.

Doing so helps the researcher avoid counterarguments.

Doing so minimizes the difficulty of interpreting the research findings.

6. What is the primary benefit of joining a writing group while conducting dissertation research?⁶

It affords the researcher valuable feedback from peers, fosters accountability, and instills the discipline necessary for a successful write-up.

It helps the researcher avoid plagiarism and streamline their research with other similar ones, reducing their individual workload.

It enhances the researcher's ability to conduct individualized studies.

It guarantees that the researcher's dissertation will be published.

7. The primary intent of any dissertation research is⁷

To investigate, in a systematic manner, a socially significant research question that adds to existing literature and demonstrates the student's ability to conduct original research.

⁵ Turabian, sec. 3.1.2, 5.4.3 (2).

⁶ Turabian, sec. 2.5.

⁷ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 1.

- To fulfill the required credits for a PhD program.
 - To provide the readers with a focused review of the subject matter literature.
 - To prepare the student for an academic position in higher institutions.
8. What are the four main components of a typical dissertation research?⁸
- Dissertation Concept Paper, Dissertation Prospectus, Dissertation, and Dissertation Manuscript.**
 - Research Proposal, Preliminary Report, Peer-reviewed Paper, and Book Chapter.
 - Review of Literature, Empirical Analysis, Discussion of Results, and Policy Implications.
 - Background of the Subject, Method of Analysis, Findings, and Conclusion.
9. Unintentional researcher bias in dissertation research can be described as⁹
- Subconscious influences on the research, driven by the researcher's personal beliefs, experiences, motives, etc.**
 - Deliberate manipulation of data, results, and findings to achieve desired outcomes.
 - Intentionally generating research findings to sway the doctoral supervisory committee.
 - Undue reliance by the researcher on quantitative methods of analysis over qualitative ones.

⁸ Sampson, 2.

⁹ Sampson, 8–9.

10. What is the primary purpose of the European Commission's English Style Guide?¹⁰

- To aid English-language authors and translators working for the European Commission in producing clear, reader-friendly texts.**
- To impose strict grammatical rules for all the legal and policy documents produced by the EU.
- To normalize the use of British English across all the EU member countries.
- To provide non-EU members with a means to develop their in-house styles.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth Edition (Brussels, 2021), 4.